

Formation and Isolation of Heterometallic Manganese Clusters with Cobalt and Iron from $\text{CpMnCo}(\text{CO})_5\text{PPhH}$ ($\text{Cp} = \eta^5\text{-Cyclopentadienyl}$, $\text{Ph} = \text{Phenyl}$)

RAJIB LAL DE* and SANJIB KUMAR BHAR

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 24 February 1993, revised 10 February 1994, accepted 17 February 1994

The reactions of $\text{CpMnCo}(\text{CO})_5\text{PPhH}$ with $\text{K}[\text{Co}(\text{CO})_4]$ and $\text{K}[\text{CpFe}(\text{CO})_2]$ in toluene : tetrahydrofuran (5 : 1) medium at -80° under mild vacuum in 1 : 1 molar ratios lead to the formation of two heterometallic trinuclear cluster compounds, $\text{CpMnCo}_2(\text{CO})_4(\mu_2\text{-CO})_3(\mu_3\text{-PPh})$, $\text{Cp}_3\text{MnFe}_2(\mu_2\text{-CO})_3(\mu_3\text{-PPh})$. The tetranuclear cluster, $\text{Cp}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_4(\mu_2\text{-CO})_2(\mu_4\text{-PPh})_2$ is also formed along with one already known product.

Facile reactivity of the P-X (X = H or Cl) bonds towards metal carbonyls are being demonstrated to lead to the simultaneous generation of P-M and as well as M-M bonds^{1,2}. Recently, we have reported the reactions of $\text{CpMnCo}(\text{CO})_5\text{PPhH}$ (**1**) with some metal carbonyls which yielded hetero/homometallic cluster compounds but failed to produce any heterometallic cluster compound containing manganese atom³.

Dehydrogenation reactions of **1** with a few suitable metal carbonyl anions have been studied with a view to see the possible formation of higher nuclear heterometallic manganese clusters. The results obtained from the reactions of **1** with $\text{K}[\text{Co}(\text{CO})_4]$ and $\text{K}[\text{CpFe}(\text{CO})_2]$ are reported here.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of the products obtained by the reaction of **1** and metal carbonyls indicated the disappearance and/or appreciable shortening of some of the bands shown by the starting complex **1**, and appearance of a few newer reasonably sharp bands, suggesting appreciable reaction. When the reaction mixture was

allowed to reflux for longer time (~20 h), the products appeared to undergo some sort of decomposition/change as observed in the ir spectra which showed broadening of the ν_{CO} bands.

At ~6 h reaction time, the clusters $\text{CpMnCo}_2(\text{CO})_4(\mu_2\text{-CO})_3(\mu_3\text{-PPh})$ (**2b**, dark red solid) were formed. Two tetranuclear species $\text{Co}_4(\text{CO})_8(\mu\text{-CO})_2(\mu_4\text{-PPh})_2$ (**3a**, red solid) and $\text{Cp}_2\text{Co}_2\text{Fe}_2(\text{CO})_4(\mu_2\text{-CO})_2(\mu_4\text{-PPh})_2$ (**3b**, black crystalline solid) were also formed in small amounts. Compound **3a** is known to form when the compound **1** and also $\text{CpMn}(\text{CO})_2\text{PPhH}_2$ were brought into reactions with $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ ²⁻⁴. Established synthetic method⁵ is available for **3a**.

At ~20 h reaction time, **3a** and **3b** were found to be the main products with higher yields. The formation of mainly tetranuclear compounds **3a** and

3b supports the fact that higher nuclear cluster formation requires longer reaction time or in other words vigorous reaction conditions are not favourable for the stability of the manganese containing cluster compounds in general and for **2a** and **2b** in particular. In the ir spectra, ν_{CO} band appeared at 2100–1900 and 1900–1800 cm^{-1} suggesting the presence of both the terminal as well as the CO-groups bridged between the two metal atoms in **2a** and **3b**. The exact positions of the ν_{CO} bands indicated the presence of $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_5$ groups⁵. For **2b**, on the other hand, ν_{CO} bands were observed only at 1900–1800 cm^{-1} suggesting the presence of only CO-groups bridged between the two metal atoms. The presence of limited ν_{CO} bands suggest highly symmetric nature of the molecules. The ^1H nmr spectra, indicated the presence of cyclopentadienyl group (δ 4.6–4.9) for **2a**, **3b** showed the presence of a doublet in the cyclopentadienyl region whereas a multiplet appeared in case of **2b** in the cyclopentadienyl region which is suggestive of the presence of more than one and at least two different types of cyclopentadienyl groups. The appearance of a doublet with low J value (2.4 Hz) also supports the presence of CpFe groups as *cis* to each other in **3b**. Mass spectra showed successive loss of CO groups and sufficient stability of metal-PPh groups. Results of elemental analyses and molecular weight determinations by mass spectral method agree well with their formulations (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **2a**, **b**, **3b**

Compd. no. (M.p. °C)	Mol. formula (Mol. wt. m/z)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	Co/Fe
2a (122d)	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{10}\text{Co}_2\text{MnO}_7\text{P}$ (543)	41.01 (39.78)	1.93 1.84	20.98 21.73
2b (137d)	$\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{Fe}_2\text{MnO}_3\text{P}$ (494)	59.00 (58.29)	3.87 4.05	22.11 22.27
3b (148d)	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{Co}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_6\text{P}_2$ (744)	45.03 (45.16)	2.58 2.69	16.14 15.86

Experimental

All experiments were performed under nitrogen atmosphere. The organic solvents used were dried and distilled before use. Silica gel 60 was made water-free at $\sim 160^\circ$ under reduced pressure.

The compound **1** was prepared by the reported

method². $\text{CpMn}(\text{CO})_3$ ⁵, $\text{K}[\text{Co}(\text{CO})_4]$ ⁷ and $\text{K}[\text{CpFe}(\text{CO})_2]$ ⁷ and PPhH_2 ⁸ were prepared by the literature methods.

Ir spectra (CH_2Cl_2) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a FX-100 spectrometer at I.I.C.B., Calcutta, using trimethylsilane as internal standard and mass spectra and C, H analyses were performed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Metal contents were estimated by standard spectrophotometric methods.

Reactions of 1 with metal carbonyl salts : Compound **1** (1.5 mmol) dissolved in toluene (25 ml) and the metal carbonyl salts (1.5 mmol) dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml) were mixed together at room temperature and allowed to react for ~ 2 h and the temperature was raised slowly to $\sim 80^\circ$ and a mild vacuum was applied when the reaction mixture started boiling and allowed to reflux for ~ 6 – 20 more hours. It was then cooled to room temperature, filtered to remove undissolved materials, the volume reduced to ~ 5 ml and then chromatographed over a silica gel column. The fractions collected by eluting with n-hexane-toluene (5 : 1), then solvent removed and the products were crystallised from n-hexane-toluene (5 : 1) to yield compounds **2a**, **b** and **3a**, **b**. Reaction time of ~ 6 h yielded **2a** (0.31 g, 38%), **2b** (0.24 g, 29%), **3a** (0.13 g, 12%), **3b** (0.18 g, 17%), and reaction time ~ 20 h yielded **2a** (0.09 g, 11%), **2b** (0.11 g, 13%), **3a** (0.22 g, 20%), **3b** (0.20 g, 19%).

Acknowledgement

The author thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support to one of them (S.K.B.).

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